
CLOUD BASED INTERNET of THINGS (IoT) ARCHITECTURE FOR HEPATITIS DIAGNOSIS

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Abstract

The paper began by taking a look at the general concept of IoT, what it entails and how the autonomous sensors and actuators are coordinated through special communications protocols. Related works in healthcare IoT system came in handy in determining the direction of this research. Healthcare solutions are usually time critical tasks, therefore the need for timely response of changes in human system. Healthcare solution of interest to this research is formulated around the deadly scourge of Hepatitis disease. Hepatitis is curable but only when it is detected within the first four months of its invasion into human system, otherwise when it stays undetected for longer period it degenerates into irreversible cancer of the liver commonly known as Liver Cirrhosis or Hepatocellular carcinoma. Hence, non-invasive Hepatitis biosensors are explored for implementation driven through IoT cloud technology architecture for timely diagnosis of the ailment to mitigate its danger. The research sought for details on hepatitis screening process by conducting a survey of eminent hospitals in the metropolis of Jos, the capital of Plateau State, Nigeria. A conclusion was drawn by recommending the adoption of the designed architecture by technology companies to come up with wearable for Hepatitis diagnosis along numerous recommendations on medical best practices around hepatitis mitigation and treatment.

Keywords: IoT-Cloud, Healthcare Architecture, Hepatitis Diagnosis, Routine Opt-Out Test

1.0 Introduction

Internet of Things (IoT) comprises a collection of innovations that drives a plethora of appliances, devices, and objects (or simply “things”) to relate and communicate spontaneously with one another through special communication protocols (Aboubakar et al., 2022). People are directly involved in the processes that give rise to the majority of data and information that exist on the Internet in most cases, however, in IoT, embedded components are frequently the active element that provides the information (Bellini et al., 2023). There are many applications for IoT including healthcare system, which is the focus of this research. Healthcare systems harness a gamut of networked gadgets to implement an IoT platform dedicated for the provision of healthcare diagnostics, such as evaluating a patient’s body system and spontaneously identifying cases where medical advices are eminent (Laplante & Laplante, 2016). Therefore, to better comprehend the importance of this technology a few examples are provided thus; Firstly, for patient suffering from bulimia (eating disorder) in a hospital or home care setting, sensors in the patient’s room could detect increased body temperature or blood pressure, or even the odour of vomit and report such in real time for prompt response (Catarinucci, 2017). Secondly, monitoring in hospitals can take many paths. Staff may try to keep certain equipment, such as Intravenous (IV) pump or oxygen tanks, in their unit for future use. In a hospital, scarce shared equipment such as Electrocardiogram (EKG) machines, Intravenous (IV) pumps, Ventilators and patient-controlled analgesia (PCA) medication pumps could be tracked via IoT technology (Sato et al., 2013).

Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) and Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infections are major causes of severe and chronic liver disease, such as cirrhosis and Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC) globally, and caused an estimated 1.5 million deaths yearly (World Health Organization, 2021). Consequently, a Cloud-based IoT solution was proposed to monitor and report in real-time the response of the patient to the treatment of hepatitis B with respect to various hepatitis B drugs such as lamivudine, tenofovir, adefovir, telbivudine, entecavir (Xie et al., 2021). However, healthcare solutions are time critical domain with high risk in diagnostic response delay (Chevaliez & Pawlotsky, 2020). Healthcare systems in general require reliable and fast response time. Any drop in data, as well as monitoring results, might be irreversibly harmful for the users, for example, in stroke, diabetes, Alzheimer’s, or fall monitoring systems, it is imperative to monitor the patients without interruptions, and any kind of delays in transmission or monitoring might prove fatal for the patients (Islam et al., 2020). Hence, the quality of service such as improved latency, reduced energy demand, efficient memory and bandwidth utilization in IoT Cloud-based healthcare solution should be the primary focus of IoT Cloud-based healthcare solution (Tuli et al., 2021).

1.1 Statement of the Problem

About 304 million people were living with viral hepatitis B and C in 2022 (World Health Organization, 2024). An estimated 254 million were living with hepatitis B and 50 million were living with hepatitis C. Research priorities for viral hepatitis response include improved *in vitro* diagnostic medical devices and testing approaches for simplified, timely and accurate diagnosis of chronic Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) and Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) infections, including core antigen rapid diagnostic tests for HCV; multiplex testing and diagnostics for HBV, including rapid diagnostic tests (Hajarizadeh et al., 2023). Typically, these tests procedures present barriers to screening hepatitis B and hepatitis C such as tedious laboratory procedures, phlebotomy resources onsite and offsite, healthcare provider capacity, provider comfort and interest in completing screening and treatment, provider knowledge of

HCV/HBV or of current screening recommendations, stigma, cost, and other contributors to patient refusals (World Health Organization, 2024).

Therefore, Center for Disease Control (CDC) was tasked with a short-term outcome of increased HCV and/or HBV testing in health systems (HS) (Ezzat et al., 2023). The health system assessment (HSA) should be used to work toward enhancing HCV and HBV screening process, and to identify opportunities for systems-level improvements to support reaching viral hepatitis elimination. This aim should be built around ways to identify, describe and assess gaps in current and potential health system capacity for viral hepatitis testing that will deliver the following goals (World Health Organization, 2024):

- i. Improve provider education on the use of technology to integrate and simplify screening
- ii. Achieve efficient and effective Routine, opt-out HCV and HBV screening
- iii. Removes the stigma associated with HCV testing
- iv. Fosters earlier diagnosis and treatment
- v. Reduces risk of transmission
- vi. Improve cost-effectiveness
- vii. Strengthen public health surveillance
- viii. Improve engagement and continuity of care to treat and cure viral hepatitis
- ix. Improve and develop strategies to increase patient and provider awareness

1.2 Aim and Objectives

The objective of this research is to design a cloud-based IoT architecture for the implementation of efficient and effective technology to undertake routine opt-out HCV and HBV screening that can meet the recommended goals of the WHO, 2024 report, through the following objectives:

- i. Conduct qualitative and quantitative survey of five (5) major hospitals within Jos metropolis, in plateau state regarding HBV and HCV screening processes.
- ii. Code and analyze the surveyed data using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) tool.
- iii. Identify barriers and challenges in line with the World Health Organization (WHO) recommended routine opt-out test for timely detection, cure and elimination of HBV and HCV from the result of the analysis conducted.
- iv. Provide tailored recommendations on how to surmount the identified challenges and barriers through the use of cloud-based IoT technology.
- v. Design the cloud-based IoT architecture for efficient and effective routine opt-out test for HBV and HCV.

1.3 Organization of paper

Section 1 of the paper discussed different examples of cloud-based IoT architecture in healthcare system to provide an overview of the study. The section proceeded to streamline

the concept of cloud-based IoT technology in providing solution to barriers and challenges associated with routine opt-out screening of hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus to complement existing hospital system's procedures as indicated in world health organization report of 2024, that technology should be integrated in the screening process of hepatitis B and hepatitis C to enhance the screening process. Section 2 focused on related literatures on cloud-based IoT architectures in healthcare system, and discussed the possibilities of integrating existing research on nano technology related to hepatitis B and hepatitis C screening into cloud-based IoT architecture for real-time noninvasive detection of the disease before it deteriorates further. In section 3, detailed methodology regarding the steps and activities necessary for conducting successful survey in identifying those challenges and barriers for screening hepatitis B virus and hepatitis C virus in hospital system and the possibilities of integrating technology in the screening process for effective and efficient outcome of the screening process were discussed. A tailored survey instrument was carefully designed in line with the research aim and objectives. Section 4 will center on the discussion of the result of the analyzed data and the solution to proffer based on the outcome, through the cloud-based IoT architecture that forms the research goal. Section 5 captures the summary, conclusion and recommendations of the research.

2.0 Literature Review

This section looked at related works to cloud-based IoT healthcare systems by exploring the various methods, approaches, models and technologies deployed to improve on the performance of existing Cloud-based IoT healthcare Systems. Cloud based IoT healthcare typically comprised of the front-end and the back-end. The front-end is made of the Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) that communicate with each other either via Bluetooth, ZigBee, Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi), Radio Frequency Identifier (RFID) or similar compatible wireless communication protocols.

2.1 The Concept of Internet of Things (IoT)

Kevin Ashton initially proposed the term IoT in 1999 in a presentation to Proctor and Gamble executives (Thurston & De-Leon, 2018). The idea was coined from the notion that most of the data generated on the internet was through exclusive human activities such as information retrieval, video streaming, file sharing, online shopping, banking, social networking, and many more activities. Conversely, the same activities can be performed through things autonomously communicating with themselves without human intervention, this new world of connected devices is called the IoT (Mishra & Swades, 2017). Consequently, the major IoT application domain in practice utilizing the IoT concepts are summarized into smart cities, smart homes, vehicular systems, healthcare, industries, sports and leisure (Mathieu et al., 2017). IoT ranks high in evolving the approach to work life. Therefore, robust IoT technology and concepts were designed and developed to include machine-to-machine (M2M) communications, Radio Frequency Identification (RFID), Location Based Services (LBS), Lab-on-chip (LOC) sensors, Augmented Reality (AR), robotics and vehicle telematics, etc. (Katzis & Ahmadi, 2017). However, even though there are many areas of application of IoT in real life, the focus of this research is in the field of healthcare hence the need to streamline to fit into context.

2.2 Healthcare Telemedicine and Wearable Applications

Healthcare solutions span a wide range of functions, from intensive care to health monitoring of healthy individuals for preventive health and public health purposes. Stakeholders for healthcare IoT include patients and their families, healthcare professionals, provider organization, insurance payers, and regulatory agencies such as the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) (Thurston & De-Leon, 2018). Patients with critical conditions

need to be monitored and sensors should be able to detect abnormal values in real-time and alert authorities concern such as doctor, hospital and family (Mathieu et al., 2017). This will require the deployment of several sensors in clothes, watches, wearable accessories, even jewels in order to continuously monitor the blood pressure, heartbeat, blood glucose level, blood oxygen level, standing position and many other body system ratings (Mishra & Swades, 2017).

Therefore, it is possible to imagine sensor, which can remind people to take their medication, or even to suggest increasing or reducing their prescribed quantities according to the current value of some monitored metrics like glucose levels for diabetes, and blood pressure. Furthermore, for ill and injured people, IoT could also allow such people to stay living at home (instead of being at the hospital), but under the monitoring of many IoT sensors, which could monitor various aspects of the person's body, control some actions and remotely inform doctors if needed (Michalopoulos et al., 2015). A practical example is iHealthBag as shown in Figure 2.2, which is an Arduino device IoT implementation (Aneke et al., 2018). This model deploy devices and tools to detect and report changes in disparate sensitive metrics (such as heart rate, temperature, Electrocardiogram (ECG), blood pressure, glucose, pulse), to send alarms in case of anomalies, and to manage medicine consumption.

Figure 2.2: iHealthBag Caregiver App Prototype (Aneke et al., 2018)

However, the limitations of this technique are scalability and energy inefficiency due to heavy applications running on mobile device supported by a battery source. In addition, the permeating sensors of the IoT, as shown in Figure 2.3, can collate enormous volumes of data that could be used to bring about breakthrough in different fields of research through big data analytics (Sholla et al., 2017). Furthermore, IoT has the possibility to accommodate a plethora of healthcare solutions such as health monitoring, machine-controlled surgeries, automated prescriptions, and therapy, implants, real-time diagnostics agents, fitness adviser, care attendants and other evolving needs in healthcare system, hence the need for accuracy and scalability is imperative (Al-Fuqaha et al., 2015).

Figure 2.3: Connected Smart Healthcare (Sholla et al., 2017)

A more flexible system was proffered as shown in Figure 2.4, this system provided a cloud service for resource scalability and also segment the systems operations into functional and non-functional requirements through an Extensible Markup Language (XML) setting (Renta et al., 2017). This setup specifies the operations the system can perform for the users and the responsibilities that must be periodically adjusted by the user, thereby rendering the system prone to human errors due to periodic adjustments, further some emergency metric reading could risk being overlooked. Consequently, an interoperability algorithm was implemented to enable auto adjustment by the system to integrate external supportive services for improved medical healthcare delivery (DePalo & Song, 2012).

Figure 2.4: Modified Healthcare System Architecture with IoT Device as Frontend and Cloud Services as Backend (Renta et al., 2017).

2.3 Evaluating Acute Ailments through Wearable Devices

Acute infections can cause an individual to have an elevated Resting Heart Rate (RHR) and change their routine daily activities due to the physiological response to the inflammatory result. Consequently, research was conducted that evaluated if population trends of seasonal respiratory infections, such as Influenza, could be identified through wearable sensors that collect RHR and sleep data, the process was found to be efficient and satisfactory (Radin et al., 2020). In another premise to study the effect of change in body system of human with respect to throughput during rigorous activity, wearable devices were seen as most

appropriate option for the collection of necessary body system metrics (Avina et al., 2016). This project collected real-time data on attributes related to health and performance on an extreme task through the use of commercial off-the-shelf devices to collect physiological and human performance data in real-time.

Many solutions to medical situations were demonstrated using wearable devices. A typical scenario for the adoption of wearable devices in medical healthcare solution can be seen in case of managing chronic diseases such as diabetes, heart disease and autonomous time warp algorithm for timely diagnosing of Alzheimer (Wan et al., 2018). The biodata collected from these wearable devices is often passed to a mobile phone which act as a gateway to the datacenter. This is due to the less processing power of the wearable devices that needs to be complemented by a mobile phone (Verma et al., 2018).

However, with the advances in technological development, the biodata collected by the sensor devices can be transmitted directly from the sensors to the cloud server for real time analysis and diagnosis (Javid & Mirzaei, 2021). Hence, a wearable sensor medical solution was implemented to read heartbeat, blood pressure and temperature of a patient and then send the generated medical biodata to the cloud server, via a Wireless Fidelity (Wi-Fi) technology emanating from an Arduino, Figure 2.5 (Wan et al., 2018). The data communicated to the Arduino is transmitted to the cloud server for analysis and diagnostic message transfer to the patient and the medical experts for advices in respect to heart disease detection.

Figure 2.5: Modified Wearable Sensor IoT Healthcare System (Wan et al., 2018)

Further, identified among pertinent reasons for the cause of chronic hepatitis B is the resistance to antiretroviral treatment of the hepatitis B virus. Most often than not this setback is associated with the efficacy rate of the drug used in administering the treatment. Consequently, the IoT setup in Figure 2.6 (Xie et al., 2021) was proposed to monitor and report in real-time the response of the patient to the treatment of hepatitis B with respect to various hepatitis B drugs such as lamivudine, tenofovir, adefovir, telbivudine, entecavir. However, earlier detection of the hepatitis virus through reliable IoT sensors can mitigate the risk of advancing the disease to its chronic stage.

Figure 2.6: Model for Nucleoside Drug Treatment of Hepatitis B and Liver Cirrhosis (Xie et al., 2021).

2.4 Electronic Prognosis of Hepatitis

It was earlier stated that the research will rely on simulated Hepatitis sensor data, this is necessitated by the affordability of the physical sensor, therefore, it is necessary to discuss electronic prognosis of Hepatitis for clearer understanding of the research pathway. Hepatitis-B virus have threatened the world over with its dreaded scourge and devastating effect to lives. Research has shown that about two hundred and fifty-seven (257) million people across the world are infected by hepatitis-B virus and out of this demography over 350 were confirmed to fall within the chronic hepatitis-B stage (Verma et al., 2018). The research determined that Hepatitis-B surface Antigen (HBsAg) clearance was only efficient in evaluating treatment response in patients with chronic hepatitis-B. Hence, for early detection processes more parameters such as liver thickness and width, the level of Alanine aminotransferase (ALT), serum Albumin (ALB), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST), Gamma-Glut-amyl Transferase (GGT), Direct bilirubin (Dbil), Total bilirubin (Tbil) and levels of erythrocyte and leucocyte were used (Radwan et al., 2018). It was for this reason, that further study was conducted to sought for the best machine learning algorithm, among Random Forest (FR), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Logistic Regression (LR) and Decision Tree (DCT), in the prediction of hepatitis-B. The erythrocyte and leucocyte were measured using auto-biochemical analyzer, which provides readings for Platelet (PLT), Hemoglobin (Hb), and White Blood Cell (WBC) counts. The result of the analyzed data showed that the performances of XGBoost, RF, DCT, and LR were 0.891%, 0.829%, 0.619 and 0.680%, respectively (Tian et al., 2019). Hence, XGBoost performed better than the rest of the algorithm in the prediction of hepatitis-B virus level.

Hepatitis C is a curable chronic liver disease which if not detected early and treated can metamorphose into fibrosis, hence the limitation of machine learning algorithm on data collected over time. Fibrosis is a condition where numerous fibrous connecting tissues grows in the liver, and gradually developed into Cirrhosis, an extreme liver condition beyond cure, and at this stage the only remedy for this is the highly expensive liver transplant (Mada et al., 2020). Consequently, this prompted the need to discover a faster and regular means for detecting the presence of hepatitis C in patients besides the conventional histology biopsy of hepatitis C. Histology refers to the act of tracing hepatitis C by means of microscopic study of internal tissue of patient from either blood samples or other body fluids. However, a more reliable and timelier noninvasive and percutaneous, that is devoid of skin piercing technique, of detecting hepatitis C was performed. This was done with the aim of deciding which among these three techniques: Fibrosis-4-score (FIB-4), Aspartate aminotransferase to Alanine

Aminotransferase Ratio (AAR), and Aspartate aminotransferase to Platelet Ratio Index (APRI) gives the best degree of predicting hepatitis C (Xie et al., 2021). During this process, percutaneous data of 500 patients undergoing hepatitis C biopsy was used and the result showed that FIB-4 performed better in the detection of fibrosis, which indicate the existence of hepatitis C in the patient. The limitation of the research was that it could not determine specifically if the symptoms was that of hepatitis B or hepatitis C, hence the 500 patients were first screened for hepatitis B through the conventional histology biopsy and were confirmed negative to hepatitis B prior to the percutaneous biopsy (Kisling et al., 2019).

In a similar approach machine learning algorithms comprising of Naïve Bayes, Decision Tree and neural Network were applied on data collected from 859 hepatitis C patients treated at an Egyptian national liver disease referral center. The distribution of the data was such that 602 was set aside as training data set and the remaining 257 served as the test data. Random sampling technique was adopted in extracting both the training and test data from the source in order to eliminate bias. The finding from the classification showed that Decision Tree performed better in predicting hepatitis C with accuracy rate of 50% followed by Neural Network with prediction accuracy of rate 49% and lastly Naïve Bayes with 46% (Radwan et al., 2018). The determination to achieving impeccable solution to the health challenges posed by hepatitis B kept gaining more zeal to explore better avenues of mitigation by the research community. Part of the barriers militating against effective healthcare delivery among Asian American in the United State living with chronic hepatitis B is the communication gap that existed between the patients and health care practitioner due to deficiency in language proficiency (Hyun et al., 2020).

Therefore, to overcome this and promote active involvement of hepatitis B patients in access to healthcare service, a texting app called “HelpTalk” was improvised to bridge the communication gap (World Health Organization, 2021). HelpTalk is a bidirectional messaging app that was experimented among 82 Korean American participants infected with Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) identified through community campaign against HBV in New York. It was observed that the frequency of messages sent and responded to falls between 8 to 14 messages per participant and healthcare practitioner. The result of themes of the messages recorded after 6 months of the study was analyzed and it was confirmed that 78 out of the 82 participants were connected to adequate healthcare service in six months.

Liver biopsy through the invasive means is gradually becoming unattractive to both the patients and the healthcare practitioners because of its perceived traumatic tendency, hence the devising of microarray, a certified and mainstream technology for effective provision of vivid picture of gene expression to aid in surface biopsy of the liver (Zhou et al., 2017). Microarray technology was deployed alongside machine learning algorithms specifically Random Forest (RF), K-Nearest Neighbor (KNN) and SVM on record of 122 patients screened with chronic HBV. Serum clinical parameters particularly Alanine Aminotransferase (ALT), Aspartate aminotransferase (AST) and HBV Deoxyribonucleic Acid (DNA) together with liver inflammation parameters and gene expression were analyzed using the stated machine learning algorithms for likely relationship between them. The result showed that it is extremely possible to perform chronic HBV detection using surface body fluid (Verma et al., 2018). Outcome of researches such as the ones discussed in this section can be used to complement the design of noninvasive hepatitis sensors that will form the discussions in the later part of this work.

2.5 Hepatitis B and C Biosensors

Biosensor is an intelligent gadget for sensing biological components and translating it into physiochemical indicator (Yao & Fu, 2014). Substantial medical research on biosensor centered on immunological features or DNA hybridization whose resultant effect is instant feedback with outstanding sensitivity is gaining interest. Biosensors for detection of hepatitis B have been implemented leveraging on the technological power behind the operating principles of optical signals, electrochemistry, acoustic wave technology, and nanotechnology (Huang et al., 2014). An array of some biosensor built on these stated technologies that are of relevance to this research are discussed as follows:

- i. **Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance (LSPR):** This is an innovative gold nanotechnology biosensor designed around localized surface Plasmon resonance, specifically for the detection of HBsAg. Evaluating the reliability of the test process proved that Hepatitis B surface (HBs) antibody sticking to the nanotechnology rod justified that direct adsorption and continuous solidification on the surface of the rod forms elastic shell covering on the rod, which ensures specific compound adsorption thus permitting the analysis to take place in plasma and serum. The outcome of this confirmed that a gold nanotechnology rod LSPR biosensor can estimate HBsAg saturation at a level as low as 0.01 International Unit IU/mL which is 40 times smaller than the saturation laboratory assay is capable of detecting (Yao & Fu, 2014). The LSPR biosensor can be deployed in a quantitative analysis of HBsAg with a concentration range of between 0.01 to 1 IU/mL, and it provides the advantage of direct detection of HBV without any addition label as well as offering the opportunity for online analysis to be performed (Huang et al., 2014). Hence, early detection is guaranteed before the disease spread all over the body system and proper measures can be taken to mitigation the effect of the disease on time.
- ii. **DNA Biosensor:** This biosensor was built based on electrochemical transducers, which are considered perfect option to deliver good sensitivity, excellent specificity, and ease of applicability at extremely low cost for transforming nucleic acid hybridization reaction into quantitative signal (Faruk et al., 2013). The electrochemical DNA biosensor is capable of detecting HBV DNA by analyzing the covalent immobilization of the 21-mer residue in the peptide (where mer is a suffix for polymer) or the number of residues per amino acid in a single stranded DNA (ssDNA) which are useful indicators of HBV gene. The throughput of the electrochemical DNA biosensor on the detection of HBV DNA was confirmed to stand at range between 1.01×10^{-8} to 1.62×10^{-6} mol/L (moles/Liter) (Sato et al., 2013). Hence, the DNA biosensor can be used for confirmatory detection of HBV DNA in human system for analytical purposes.
- iii. **Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM) Biosensor:** This biosensor was developed centrally on the attributes of American Technology (AT) quartz crystal oscillator that oscillate with the passage of Alternating Current (AC) through it. Usually, the quartz surface is coated with thin gold metal, which serve both as a conductor for the AC and collection layer for bio receptor to be analyzed. The deposit of the bio substance is measured by weighing the change in the frequency resulting from the additional mass on the gold metal layer due to the collected bio-substance. QCM biosensor provides advantages such as the possession of compact size, great sensitivity, good specificity, affordability and rapid response (Catarinucci, 2017). The QCM biosensor through an immunoassay chip embedded in it can detect

HBV and antibodies in less than 2-hours. The frequency adjuster indicator provided a detection limit of 0.1 nanograms per milliliter ng/mL and autonomous detection range of 0.1 to 10000 (ng/mL) for both HBsAg and antibodies with added advantage of rapid, sensitive and specific detection of HBV (Mathieu et al., 2017).

- iv. **Micro-Cantilever Biosensor:** This is a viable biosensor with outstanding performance qualities (Huang et al., 2014). It uses advanced micro nano-electromechanical system, which informed its obtrusive application in the field of nano-biotechnology. Micro cantilever biosensor has the advantage of rapid detection, intuitive operation mode, affordability, label-free detection in complex biological serum. Hence, this biosensor has been deployed successfully in immunoassay, DNA hybridization and hepatitis virus detection (Fetjah et al., 2021). The micro cantilever biosensor features a built in DNA sensing System-on-a-Chip (SoC) that has sensors, electronic processor, wireless connectivity, and connection interface for HBV DNA detection. The HBV DNA SoC can successfully detect HBV DNA with an estimated concentration range of 1picomole (pmol) to 10 nanomole (nmol) (Avina et al., 2016).
- v. **Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) Biosensor:** This biosensor is a class of piezoelectric sensors with extreme speed, sensitivity, specificity and reliability. This sensor uses low wave pattern SAW immuno-sensors to detect hepatitis B surface
- vi. antibodies with greater sensitivity to HBsAg. Performance of this sensor indicates a proportionate linearity between the frequency shift of the biosensor and the concentration of the hepatitis B surface antibodies at estimated sensitivity of 0.74 hertz (Hz) per microliter (μ L). The sensor is capable of successfully detecting HBV at a detection limit of less than 10 picogram (pg)/ μ L(Wan et al., 2018).

2.6 Advances in Healthcare IoT Quality of Service (QoS) Optimization

One of the main reasons for the study is that, time-sensitive healthcare IoT applications need low latency and good services. All of these requirements simply cannot be met in the cloud. Because patients' physiological states change over time, it is important to make decisions quickly and respond quickly to remote patient's needs. Latency can be increased by unusually unpredictable conditions in the network. It is impossible to return patient health data in real time because of high latency (Fetjah et al., 2021). As a result, such data are invalid, incorrect, and untrustworthy. Cascading-based data processing, such as the processing of electrocardiogram (ECG) and electroencephalogram (EEG) signals, presents a more significant issue. Some attempts made in reducing latency in this regard includes; the deployment of 5G network time slicing for channel access and routing to augment the 10ms response time requirement of remote surgery procedure (Mustefa et al., 2021). Another attempt to reduced latency was achieved by combining Reinforcement Learning with Greedy Algorithm to create an algorithm described as Optimized Latency Fog Computing (OLFC) model (Aiswarya et al., 2022). The OLFC model categorized medical data into high, low and normal risk to prioritize medical response time of remote patient monitoring system. The outcome of the OLFC model was evaluated against existing, IFogStor model (Naas et al., 2017), and the conventional Fog Computing (FC) model. Thus, the result reported 52% and 30% latency reduction, 1.5% and 0.7% lower Bandwidth utilization, 12% and 6% lower energy consumption against iFogStor and FC models, respectively. Furthermore, a model was designed for efficient cloud based IoT vehicle routing problem using a resource

management algorithm called Reliable Resource Allocation Management (R2AM) algorithm on iFogSim2 simulator with 15 fog devices, and an installed Decentralized Decision System (DDS) for resource management (Atig et al., 2023). The IoT response time and energy consumption obtained from the R2AM algorithm as compared to the result of one of the existing algorithms, called Scalable Microservices Placement (SMP) (Mahmud et al., 2018), showed that R2AM has 10.3% lower latency and 21.85% lower energy usage than that of SMP algorithm. However, R2AM has limitation for execution failure due to the limited number of fog devices used (Atig et al., 2023). In order to further optimize cloud based IoT energy and service latency QoS, a four-tier architecture consisting of Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) layer, edge layer, fog layer, and cloud layer was presented, this was harness by categorizing the IoT generated workloads into high critical sensor data (such as heart failure rate, body temperature, glucose level rating), medium critical sensor data (such as remote patient monitoring, emergency response service, patient diagnostic, health status check), and low critical sensor data (Example, healthcare records requiring complex data analytics for future decision making), these data were offloaded into the setup using Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP) resource management model to optimize service level objective matrix specifically energy consumption and service latency of IoT cloud healthcare solution, the result obtained from the four-tier MILP model was compared against that obtained from cloud only architecture (described as baseline architecture), and the result showed that the energy consumption and service latency were optimized by 21% and 73%, respectively (Alharbi et al., 2023).

3.0 Methodology

The survey will adopt direct contact approach with the respondents albeit the easier and cost-effective online survey platforms such as the Survey-Monkey or Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap). This is due to the sensitive nature of the data to be collated. Using online survey platform may lead to obtaining responses from non-professionals that do not have the requisite knowledge of Hepatitis B Virus (HBV) and Hepatitis C Virus (HCV) screening, test, treatment and care. This consideration is in line with the guidelines of stratified sampling technique, when your focused group should be strictly streamline around a desired criteria for reliable responses as against a random sampling technique which allow respondents across different professional backgrounds. The focus group to be contacted will comprise practice/infrastructure administrators to identify the correct persons to answer the questions to be administered. This includes the Chief Medical Director (CMD) and existing contacts that will bridge between the researcher and the laboratory experts.

The research will adopt both qualitative and quantitative approaches. Specifically, interview and onsite observations tools will be used to capture the qualitative data and a questionnaire will form the tool to capture the quantitative data for the research. The questionnaire will capture queries about barriers to completing testing, challenges of routine opt-out screening, understanding of the disease, and possibility to mitigate these challenges and barriers through the use of technology such as wearable device. The patients' interview could yield helpful information on barriers and challenges through direct experiences, especially those related to stigmatization, cost, busy schedules, negligence to health issues that technology could come in as remedy. Observation or onsite review of processes could be time intensive, but it is worth doing. This will provide detail interaction with the laboratory staff or the healthcare providers on the intricacies of the clinical test procedures such as specimen to use, reagents needed and readings for positive and negative cases as the case may be. This could source necessary information that will guide in the design of the innovative architecture of the noninvasive nano technology wearable device.

Other sources of information that could be deployed includes the followings:

- i. Review of written protocols and test: This source comprised of ordering forms used by healthcare providers reviewing written resources that may reveal possible barriers understood as the protocol by providers and can be used to identify opportunities for improvement of test procedures.
- ii. Disease surveillance data: This source can be used to determine the prevalence HCV and HBV; it can also show the scale of testing for either positive or negative test results.
- iii. Brief patients' intercepts: This source sought for the patient's experience by asking the patient questions such as "have you ever been offered test for HBV or HCV by your healthcare provider?"

The research sample size comprised of 100 participants across the five major hospital facilities around Jos metropolis of Plateau State, Nigeria. The respondents were drawn across the major hospitals, these are; Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH), Plateau State Specialist Hospital Jos, Dadin-Kowa Specialist Hospital Jos, Our Lady Apostolic (OLA) Hospital Jos and Bingham Teaching Hospital (Jan-Kwano) Jos. Putting together all the pieces of information gathered, and analyzing them will provide recommendations for the design of technology architecture that will improve access to routine HCV and HBV testing, innovative approaches, and best practices clinical interventions as recommended in WHO, 2024 report.

4.0 Analysis of Result

This section described in detail the analysis of the surveyed data that sought for the position of the healthcare sector regarding the challenges and barriers faced with the screening and diagnosis of hepatitis, with the view of integrating technology into the process to mitigate such challenges, and consequently eliminate or reduce the spread and scourge of the disease.

4.1 Demographics

Table 4.1 shows the medical respondents. The largest groups are Immunologists (20%) and Hepatologists (17%), with the smallest representation from Liver Transplant Surgeons (3%) and Hepatitis Nurse Specialists (3%). The variety of respondents reflects diverse expertise but indicates uneven participation across specialties as the researcher is constrained by the accessible staff at the stated hospital facilities.

Table 4.2 displays the respondent's representation across the hospital facilities. Jos University Teaching Hospital (29%) and Plateau Specialist Hospital Jos (23%) dominate, while smaller contributions come from Our Lady Apostolic Hospital and Bingham Teaching Hospital (both 13%). This distribution highlights key centers contributing to the study.

Table 4.3 displays the gender distribution of the respondents. Male participants dominate the sample (63%), while females account for 37%. The gender distribution suggests a need to understand why males are overrepresented or if this aligns with medical profession staffing prevalence patterns.

Table 4.1: MEDICAL RESPONDENTS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Phlebotomist	15	15.0	15.0	15.0
	Pharmacologist	5	5.0	5.0	20.0
	Laboratory Scientist	12	12.0	12.0	32.0
	Hepatologist	17	17.0	17.0	49.0
	Gastroenterologist	8	8.0	8.0	57.0
	Infectious Disease Specialist	11	11.0	11.0	68.0
	Liver Transplant Surgeon	3	3.0	3.0	71.0
	Immunologist	20	20.0	20.0	91.0
	Virologist	6	6.0	6.0	97.0
	Hepatitis Nurse Specialist	3	3.0	3.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.2: GENDER

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	MALE	63	63.0	63.0	63.0
	FEMALE	37	37.0	37.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.3: HOSPITAL

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH)	29	29.0	29.0	29.0
	Plateau Specialist Hospital Jos	23	23.0	23.0	52.0
	Our Lady Apostolic Hospital Jos (OLAH)	13	13.0	13.0	65.0
	Bingham Teaching Hospital (Jan Kwano) Jos	13	13.0	13.0	78.0
	Dadin Kowa Specialist Hospital Jos	22	22.0	22.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

4.2 HBV and HCV Exposure Windows

This section reflects the exposure window of hepatitis B and C based on test reagents.

Table 4.4 HBsAg Exposure Window:

Most participants (81%) had an exposure window of 1 to 3 weeks, with 15% and 4% at 6 and 8 weeks, respectively. This suggests that testing and early detection occur primarily within the first three weeks.

Table 4.5 ALT Elevation Exposure Window:

ALT elevation primarily appears at 6 weeks (71%), followed by 20% at 8 weeks and only 9% at 1 to 3 weeks. This highlights a delayed physiological response compared to exposure, emphasizing the need for follow-up testing.

Table 4.6 HBV Onset Symptoms Window:

Symptoms occur predominantly between 9 to 21 weeks (74%), with earlier symptoms reported at 6 weeks (16%) and 1 to 3 weeks (10%). This delayed onset could hinder early diagnosis and treatment.

Table 4.7 HCV RNA Exposure Window:

RNA detection is prominent early, with 76% in 1 to 2 weeks and the remainder (24%) at 3 weeks. This shows RNA detection as a reliable early marker for HCV infection.

Table 4.8 HCV Onset Symptoms Exposure Window:

Symptoms most commonly manifest at 2 weeks (78%), followed by 13% at 1 week and 9% at 3 weeks. Symptom onset aligns closely with RNA detection, supporting early testing.

Table 4.9 HBV DNA Exposure Window:

HBV DNA is detected early, with 80% at 1 to 3 weeks, tapering to 12% at 6 weeks and 8% at 8 weeks. Early DNA testing appears critical for HBV management.

Table 4.4: HBsAg EXPOSURE WINDOW

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 TO 3 WEEKS	81	81.0	81.0	81.0
	6 WEEKS	15	15.0	15.0	96.0
	8 WEEKS	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.5: ALT* ELEVATION EXPOSURE WINDOW

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 TO 3 WEEKS	9	9.0	9.0	9.0
	6 WEEKS	71	71.0	71.0	80.0
	8 WEEKS	20	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.6: HBV ONSET SYMPTOMS WINDOW

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 TO 3 WEEKS	10	10.0	10.0	10.0
	6 WEEKS	16	16.0	16.0	26.0
	9 TO 21 WEEKS	74	74.0	74.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.7: HCV RNA EXPOSURE WINDOW

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 TO 2 WEEKS	76	76.0	76.0	76.0
	3 WEEKS	24	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.8: HCV ONSET SYMPTOMS EXPOSURE WINDOW

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 WEEK	13	13.0	13.0	13.0
	2 WEEKS	78	78.0	78.0	91.0
	3 WEEKS	9	9.0	9.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.9: HBV DNA EXPOSURE WINDOW

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 TO 3 WEEKS	80	80.0	80.0	80.0
	6 WEEKS	12	12.0	12.0	92.0
	8 WEEKS	8	8.0	8.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

4.3 Testing and Adherence

This section depicts the opinions of the survey with regards to adherence to HBV and HCV routine opt-out test.

Table 4.10, Recommended Routine Opt-Out Test Interval

72% of respondents recommend a 3-week interval, while 28% suggest 2 weeks. A consensus favors a slightly extended testing window of 3 weeks interval.

Table 4.11, Adherence to Recommended Interval

A striking 89% do not adhere to the recommended interval, highlighting systemic barriers or inefficiencies in compliance.

Table 4.10: RECOMMENDED ROUTINE OPT-OUT TEST INTERVAL

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	2 WEEKS	28	28.0	28.0	28.0
	3 WEEKS	72	72.0	72.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.11: ADHERANCE TO RECOMMENDED ROUTINE OPT-OUT TEST INTERVAL

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	89	89.0	89.0	89.0
	YES	11	11.0	11.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

4.4 Technology and Data Management

This section reflects the opinion of the survey regarding the deployment of technology in handling HBV and HCV screening process.

Table 4.12, Wearable Device for Routine Opt-Out Testing:

A significant majority (87%) believe wearable devices can enhance routine testing. This suggests potential for technological integration to improve adherence.

Table 4.13, Electronic Medical Record (EMR) Usage

Only 16% report using EMRs to save test results, indicating a substantial gap in data management infrastructure.

Table 4.14, Early Detection and Spread Prevention

All respondents (100%) agree that early detection can prevent disease spread. This underscores universal support for proactive testing and timely diagnosis.

Table 4.12: WEARABLE HBV & HCV DEVICE CAN ENSURE ROUTINE OPT-OUT TEST

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	13	13.0	13.0	13.0
	YES	87	87.0	87.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.13: ELECTRONIC MEDICAL RECORD IS USED TO SAVE TEST RESULTS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	NO	84	84.0	84.0	84.0
	YES	16	16.0	16.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.14: EARLY DETECTION PREVENT SPREAD

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES	100	100.0	100.0	100.0

4.5 HCV AND HBV AS COMMUNICABLE DISEASE

Table 4.15 shows that HBV & HCV Are Communicable. All respondents (100%) agreed that HBV and HCV are communicable diseases. There is unanimous awareness among respondents about the communicable nature of HBV and HCV. In Table 4.16 the means of transfer as indicated shows that Sexual Transmission: 14% of respondents, Blood Transfusion: 20%, Body Contact (Sweat): 30%, Household Sharing (Dishes & Cutlery): 23%, Syringe Sharing (Drug Abuse): 13%. The most commonly recognized means of transfer is body contact (30%), followed by household sharing (23%) and blood transfusion (20%), Syringe sharing and sexual transmission are less frequently acknowledged. Table 4.17 shows the Effects of HBV & HCV infections. Liver Cirrhosis: 55%, Hepatocellular Carcinoma: 24%, Hepatocellular Jaundice: 21%. Hence, Liver cirrhosis is the most commonly recognized consequence (55%), aligning with medical evidence as a significant effect. Awareness of other effects (carcinoma and jaundice) is lower.

Table 4.15: HBV & HCV ARE COMMUNICABLE

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	YES	100	100.0	100.0	100.0

Table 4.16: MEANS OF TRANSFER

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	SEX	14	14.0	14.0	14.0
	BLOOD TRANSFUSION	20	20.0	20.0	34.0
	BODY CONTACT (SWEAT)	30	30.0	30.0	64.0
	HOUSEHOLD (SHARED DISH & CUTLERY)	23	23.0	23.0	87.0
	SIRINCH (DRUG ABUSE)	13	13.0	13.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.17: EFFECTS OF HBV & HCV

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	LIVER CIRRHOSIS	55	55.0	55.0	55.0
	HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA	24	24.0	24.0	79.0
	HEPATOCELLULAR JAUNDICE	21	21.0	21.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

4.6 Barriers That Impact on the Uptake of HBV and HCV Test

This section identifies the primary challenges that impede HBV and HCV screening. Here is a breakdown:

In table 4.18, Top Barriers *Stigmatization of Victims (22%)*: This is the most cited barrier, indicating social stigma is a significant deterrent to testing. *Refusal to Turn Up for Tests (19%)*: Suggests reluctance or fear among individuals to engage in screening. Moderate Barriers: *Inadequate Test Reagents (16%)*: Points to systemic issues in resource availability. *Too Many Clients/Specimens at Test Centers (13%)* and *Mix-up of Test Results (13%)*: Indicate logistical and operational inefficiencies. Lesser Barriers: *Shortage of Staff (10%)*: Reflects staffing challenges. *Inconsistency in Test Results (7%)*: Represents the lowest barrier but still notable.

Table 4.19 indicates that these barriers can be mitigated through the use of noninvasive wearable HBV & HCV screening device as majority of respondents have a positive outlook regarding the potential for a noninvasive wearable device to address these barriers. Distributions in Table 4.19 shows Strongly Agree (63%) and Agree (29%): Together, 92% of respondents believe that such technology could mitigate barriers. Strongly Disagree (4%) and Disagree (4%) a small minority are skeptical, highlighting potential concerns or reservations. Furthermore, Table 4.21 depicts these reservations with use of technology to include these positions: None (67%): Most respondents do not perceive any reservations, indicating a readiness for technology integration. Expertise (22%): A significant concern is the lack of technical expertise to use advanced technology effectively. Cost (9%): Cost is a relatively minor concern, and Other/Unclear Responses (2%). In Table 20, Electronic Medical Records (EMR) can improve test procedure ordering. There is strong consensus that EMRs could enhance the test procedure as indicated, Strongly Agree (69%) and Agree (26%): Combined 95% agreement underscores confidence in EMRs as a solution for process efficiency. Disagree (5%): A small percentage have concerns, which might stem from implementation challenges or lack of familiarity.

Table 4.18: BARRIERS TO HBV & HCV SCREENING

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	INCONSISTENCY IN TEST RESULTS	7	7.0	7.0	7.0
	INADEQUATE TEST REAGENTS	16	16.0	16.0	23.0
	TOO MANY CLIENTS/SPACIMENT AT TEST CENTER	13	13.0	13.0	36.0
	SHORTAGE OF STAFF	10	10.0	10.0	46.0
	MIXUP OF TEST RESULTS	13	13.0	13.0	59.0
	STIGMATIZATION OF VICTIMS	22	22.0	22.0	81.0
	REFUSAL TO TURN UP FOR TEST	19	19.0	19.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.19: NONINVASIVE WEARABLE HBV & HCV DEVICE CAN MITIGATE THE BARRIERS

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLY AGREE	63	63.0	63.0	63.0
	AGREE	29	29.0	29.0	92.0
	STRONGLY DISAGREE	4	4.0	4.0	96.0
	DISAGREE	4	4.0	4.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.20: EMR CAN IMPROVE TEST PROCEDURE ORDERING

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	STRONGLY AGREE	69	69.0	69.0	69.0
	AGREE	26	26.0	26.0	95.0
	DISAGREE	5	5.0	5.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Table 4.21: RESERVATION WITH USE OF TECHNOLOGY

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	COST	9	9.0	9.0	9.0
	EXPERTISE	22	22.0	22.0	31.0
	NON	67	67.0	67.0	98.0
	33	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

4.7 Efficient IoT Healthcare Architecture for Hepatitis Diagnostic

The architecture is centered on the heterogeneous cloud-based IoT model in Figure 4.1 comprising of the IoT layer, the Fog layer and the cloud layer. IoT response time as well as other Service Level Objectives (SLO) are enhanced by placing numerous Fog or Edge layers closer to the users for caching of data and fast access to cloud resources. IoT devices exhibit

lower latency when accessing data from the Fog layer through the fog gateway faster than accessing directly from higher latency cloud layer that are remotely situated. However, the hosts at the fog layer have lesser computational capabilities relative to the host on the cloud layer which has greater computational powers. The functionalities that are performed at the fog layer comprised of the scheduling decision process, data caching, resource evaluation schemes, and tasks organization.

Figure 4.1: Proposed Cloud-Based IoT Healthcare System

At the cloud layer there is greater scalability of resources such as the Elastic Cloud Compute (EC2) for processing, DynamoDB for storage of unstructured data, Elastic Container Service (ECS) for configuring IoT core for interaction with users through a Simple Messaging Service (SMS). Additionally, elaborate analytical tools are provision on the cloud for detail, reliable and accurate analysis and diagnosing of ailments for users' consumption. Persistent relational databases for structured data storage are equally available through Relational Database Service (RDS). This facilitates easier data access to both users and on cloud analytical tools as well serves as data for future researches to interested individuals and corporate organizations. The EC2 which is similar to the personal computer's processor relies on the Elastic Block Store (EBS) as its permanent storage disk, the EBS provides a fast reliable data access during execution of tasks on the cloud.

Similarly, the IoT layer is where the sensors and the user devices are found in the cloud-based IoT model. In this context the sensors are streamlined to those responsible for noninvasive intercepting and sending of signals related to Hepatitis. Specifically, the sensors of interest to this paper as described are Localized Surface Plasmon Resonance (LSPR), DNA Biosensor, Quartz Crystal Microbalance (QCM), Micro-Cantilever Biosensor and Surface Acoustic Wave (SAW) Biosensor. All these sensors can be simulated using JSON codes and will be responsible for generating the workloads to be communicated to the fog layer through

the fog gateway device. The workloads will then be orchestrated into containers known as tasks to be executed on the fog broker.

Consequently, the fog broker handles the execution of tasks by making the best task scheduling decision on the data forwarded by the sensors and allocating tasks appropriately to hosts on the fog layer based on resource metrics availability such as the CPU, RAM, Disk and Network bandwidth. Since the amount of scheduling time of tasks is directly proportional to the number of hosts in the fog broker and consequently the latency of the communication response time as well as SLO execution time, it then calls for implementation of a good scheduling policy that will drastically reduce the scheduling time for optimal IoT response time and SLO outputs. The total response time of IoT device is sum of the scheduling time and the tasks execution time of a given workload (Alharbi et al., 2023). The tasks will be organized into containers on the fog broker and the sensor generated data will serve as input to the containers for allocation to host with higher resources at specific time.

5.0 Conclusion

The paper provided an elaborate perspective to the application of cloud based IoT application in healthcare sector with special concern to the devastating scourge of Hepatitis ailment. Noninvasive Hepatitis biosensors are critically analyzed for the reliable detection and diagnostic of the ailment facilitated by efficient cloud technology implementation architecture for optimized QoS realization and seamless diagnostic responses as healthcare issue are time critical tasks.

5.1 Recommendations

This research is recommended for use by the global technology leading organization for the design of a Hepatitis wearable device to mitigate the dangers and number of dead recorded globally as a result of the deadly scourge of Hepatitis. The disease is curable but only when it is detected and reported within the first four months of contacting it, and this is where IoT comes into play, before it spread into Liver-cirrhosis or Hepatocellular carcinoma which are both irreversible cancer of the liver often rarely treated through liver transplant or surgery. Other recommendations include:

- i. **Strengths:** Early detection tools like RNA and DNA testing are widely utilized. There is strong support for wearable devices and agreement on the importance of early detection.
- ii. **Challenges:** Non-adherence to testing intervals and limited EMR use are key barriers. Variability in symptoms and delayed responses may hinder timely intervention.
- iii. Increase adherence to recommended screening intervals.
- iv. Integrating technology for better compliance, and enhancing data management systems.
- v. **Testing Gaps:** Although respondents are aware of basic tests (HBsAg, anti-HCV), a substantial gap exists in understanding advanced diagnostics (HBeAg, HBV DNA, RNA tests).
- vi. **Knowledge of Effects:** Awareness of the severe outcomes (like carcinoma) can be improved.
- vii. **Educational Campaigns:** Target misconceptions about transmission modes.

- viii. **Highlight Severe Outcomes:** Stress the long-term effects of untreated HBV and HCV to encourage timely testing and treatment.
- ix. **Stigmatization and Reluctance to Test** are the most significant barriers to HBV and HCV screening, suggesting the need for awareness campaigns and community engagement.
- x. The strong belief in **noninvasive devices** and **EMRs** highlights the importance of technological innovations in addressing barriers and improving processes.
- xi. **Technical Expertise and Cost** are notable concerns for technology adoption, which may require targeted training and cost-effective solutions.

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